

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16740341

Biodegradation of Used Engine Oil – Spilled Soil By Wide Type And Genetically Optimized *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*

Aminu H^{1*}, I. M. Fakai¹ A. N. UKwani Kwaja¹, and F. A. Atiku²

**^{*1}Department of Biochemistry,
Faculty of Life Sciences
Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology Alero, Nigeria**

**²Department of Pure and Industrial Chemistry
Faculty of Physical Sciences
Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology Alero, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

Fossil fuel contribute to chemical pollution through production of petrochemical which has increased more than 15 times higher than they were in the 1950s. The terrestrial and aquatic ecosystem are seriously threatened by the accidental as well as the deliberate spill of used engine oil. Different types of process have been designed for the removal these contaminants in the environment which include physical, chemical and biological. Observations shows that physical and chemical methods further introduce more poisonous compounds in the environment and are difficult and more expensive to handle, whereas, biological methods are more effective yet in expensive techniques for cleaning up used engine oil contaminated soil and restoring soil fertility. The current study compares the rate of biodegradation of soil polluted with used engine oil using a wild type *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and a genetically optimize one. For the optimization of the activity of the organism, the *AlkB* gene was inserted in PET-21a (+) plasmid vector as an over expression vector, then it is transformed into BL21(DE3) competent *E. coli* and confirmed by colony PCR technique. A polluted soil was collected from a mechanic workshop by using the grab sampling technique and prepared for this studies isolation of the wild type organism. 1kg of unpolluted soil was contaminated with 50mls of used engine oil, 10 plastic planting pots were used each for wild type *Pseudomonas sp.* and the genetically optimized organism and 4 ports were used as control. The samples were kept under optimum condition for biodegradation. Based on the residual oil obtained after six (6) weeks of biodegradation, the gravimetric analysis result shows that there is variation in the biodegradation strength of the two bacteria. the best degradation percentage was found in the inocula that contained the Genetically optimized organism, where more than 90% of the used engine oil in all the 10 polluted soil pots was degraded. This result shows that genetic optimization of *pseudomonas aeruginosa* can enhance the rate of remediation of soil contaminated with used engine oil.

Keywords: Bioremediation, used engine oil, contaminated soil, genetically optimize organism, wild type organism, and PAHs

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In developing countries like Nigeria, millions of gallons of used engine oil with hazardous substances were produced by automobile workshops annually, these are being disposed into the environment without any form of treatment and no regulation [2]. The underground water and soil ecology have been recognized as important dangers by the released of such harmful compounds into the environment [3]. Fossil fuel and all its derivatives consumption is steadily rising among modern machine and vehicle [4]. Accidental spillage, deliberate and mechanical operation were the three (3) major source of spent engine oil into the environment [5].

Furthermore, spent oil contains both aromatic and aliphatic hydrocarbons, which when employed, can combine to form extremely toxic compounds [6]. According to numerous researches, PAHs can cause cancer, mutagenesis and teratogenicity, as well as negatively impact the immunological and neurological system [8].

PAHs belong to a broad category of hazardous materials. Primarily originating from anthropogenic sources as a result of incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, biofuels and fire from vegetation [9]. They are especially significant because of their physicochemical characteristic, for instance, their ability to be transported to a long distance and bioaccumulation [10]. Many of the PAHs generated, have toxic, carcinogenic, and mutagenic properties [11]. The US Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) has designated sixteen (16) PAHs as priority pollutants based on tier ability to cause mutation and cancer [5]. In addition to serving as valuable environmental reservoir for these harmful substances, contaminated soil (e.g. Soil from mechanic workshop) may also be used to identify the prevalence of PAHs in the environment [12].

The hydrophobic, hydrophilic, and less soluble characteristic of PAHs contributes to their recalcitrance and may have an impact on the environmental clearance of spent engine oil [9]. Therefore, it is necessary to look into efficient remediation techniques. Many physicochemical strategies are available for cleaning up engine oil and other petroleum products like diesel and kerosene; nevertheless, each process has been shown to have pros and cons [5]. Biodegradation is regarded as one of the most effective methods for recovering soil contaminated by motor oil. As a type of bioremediation, biodegradation is economical, effective, secure and environmentally friendly [3]. Among different agents employed, the most frequently reported are bacteria [12]. Numerous researches have observed that bacteria are better in biodegradation than other organisms [4]. For instance. Microbes like *Pantoea Wallisii*, *Ochrabactrum psuedintamedium*, *Streptomysces ginkgonis*, *Pseudomonas sp*, *Ruegeria sp*, *Psuedoalteromonas sp.*, *Acinobacter sp.* and *Bacillus lecheniformis* were all effectively employed for the breakdown of spent engine oil [13].

Wild strain of bacteria or fungus are not notably capable of degrading a wide range of contaminants. The growth of these organism in the polluted sites is influenced by the environmental condition, therefore, in this research study, genetically altered organism was used [14]. This process was made possible by the molecular cloning technique, which involved the creation of genetically altered organism by carefully inserting a desired gene into the intended host using expression vectors [7].

2.0 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Isolation and identification of wild type *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*

Soil samples were collected using Grab method of soil collection from three different mechanic workshops within the metropolis, Birnin Kebbi local Government of Kebbi State, Nigeria on the 13th Sep. 2023. The isolates were obtained by serial dilution of the sample following the standard protocol [13]. 1g of the soil sample from each soil was serially diluted and plated onto nutrient agar plates which were followed by incubation at 37^oC for 24 hrs. The colonies obtained were repeatedly subcultured until pure culture was obtained. The isolate were identified using colonial morphology, gram staining and conventional biochemical test [2].

2.2 Screening of used engine oil degraders

Using 250ml Erlenmeyer flasks, each containing 150 ml of minimal salt media and 5ml of used engine oil, the isolated bacteria were evaluated for their potential to use engine oil as their sole carbon source.

For fourteen days (14), the inoculation flask were incubated at room temperature on an orbital shaker set to 170 rpm. A measure of cell proliferation, was employed to screen the isolate capacity to degrade the used engine oil using a standard plate count per hour method [5].

2.3 Cloning

In this study, bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was selected as the best degrader of used engine oil as it was confirmed from the screening studies. The gene *AIKB* which code for the enzyme responsible for the catalyzation of the crucial step in biodegradation of PAHs by *P. aeruginosa*, alkane hydroxylase, was amplified using polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR). Using the primer set as adopted from the work of Al-Kanany & Othman, (2020), with restriction sites of EcoR1 in the forward primer plus (CUG) as flanking region and HindIII in the reverse primer plus (GAC) as flanking region.

For the construction of the recombinant plasmid (PET 21a+), *AIKB* and the competent cell of *E.coli* (BL21 (DE3)), the method from the work of Al-Kanany & Othman, [15] was adopted, where the PCR product and the plasmid were restricted with same two endonucleases. Heat shock method was used to transfer the recombinant plasmid into the competent *E. coli* cells. The transformed cells were incubated and shaken for 30 minutes before being pelleted and resuspended in SOD media that was then spread on an LB agar plates containing ampicillin, this was incubated for 24hrs at 37 °C, and the PCR colony strategy was performed to determine the recombinant cell.

For the SDS-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis, 120 V was used as the operation voltage for the 10% resolving gels and 80V applied to 5% stacking gels. 15ul of protein was loaded in each lane. For the staining of the gel, coomassie Brilliant Blue G-250 was used [16].

2.4 Biodegradation of PAHs in used engine oil with wild type and genetically optimized organism.

Uncontaminated soil sample was collected and sieved through 2mm mesh to ensure uniformity. To artificially pollute the soil sample, 50mls of used engine oil was mixed with 1kg of soil. The mixed used engine oil-enriched soil was watered intermittently, and allowed to undergo weathering for three weeks [3].

A total of 24 soil pots were set up. Each containing one kilo gram (1kg) unpolluted soil. 20 pots were spiked with 50mls of used engine oil while 4 pots were left unpolluted to serve as the control in this study.

A loop of bacterial inocula (both wild type and GOO.) were each sub-cultured into 50ml nutrient broth contained in 250ml conical flask. The cells were incubated, harvested, washed and standardized using the ranges provided by McFarland standards, the number of cells ranges used were 0.5×10^8 to 4.0×10^8 colony forming units (CFU) of each was set in duplicates including the control for both the wild type and the GOO. The standardized inocula in 100ml sterile distilled water was introduces into the surface of the UEO polluted soils. Likewise, 100ml of sterile distilled water alone was introduced into the surface of the unpolluted control soils. The pots were kept under optimum condition for a period of six (6) week with intermittent watering before extraction of the residual UEO degraded [6].

2.5 Extraction and Gravimetric analysis of Residual Used Engine Oil

Gravimetric analysis was used to determine the residual UEO in soil microcosms using technique outline by Ogunbisi *et al* 2022. in summary, n-Haxane (30 ml twice) (Sigma Aldreich) was used to extract residual oil from 5g of soil sample that was collected after the 6 weeks period of biodegradation for analysis from each treatment and control. In a conical flask, the soil sample and n-Hexane were shaken vigorously for approximately five minutes to guarantee that all of the remaining UEO was removed. Decanting the solvent through filter paper into a fresh 100 ml conical flask allowed for the separation of the mixture. After repeating the process, the extract was heated in 50⁰ C oven to evaporate the solvent. A delicate weighing balance was used to determine the difference between the mass of the UEO added to the soil and the residual oil extracted [17].

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Isolation and Identification

The findings shows that *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Bacillus* sp. were the dominant microorganism in the soil sample collected, other microorganisms like *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aurios* were also found but very negligible. The colonial morphology, gram staining and conventional biochemical test (i.e., catalase, oxidase, urease, motility, citrate utilization, and sugar fermentation) confirm that. The selected microorganisms were placed in a sampling bottle containing nutrient brought and kept in the refrigerator below 4°C for further usage.

3.2 Selection of the best degrading bacteria

Pseudomonas sp. and *Bacillus* sp. were able to degrade UEO in both medium, although, *Pseudomonas* sp. was found to be the best degrader among the two isolate, the finding demonstrate that there is a steady cell growth of *pseudomonas* sp. from the first 48 hours in the minimal salt media up to the last hour (336 hrs) of the experiment. Meanwhile, *Bacillus* sp. shows a rapid growth at the beginning of the experiment, but decline significantly as the experiment progress (Table.1).

Table 1: Standard plate count per hours ranging from 48 to 336

Organism	48 hrs.	96 hrs.	144 hrs.	192 hrs.	240 hrs.	288 hrs.	336 hrs.
Pseudomonas	490	528	464	2706	5000	10824	12564
Pseudomonas	942	1044	1088	2710	6421	10694	123606
Pseudomonas	592	9574	1045	2605	6155	11184	121455
Bacillus	1294	1064	1576	2018	3486	8072	9158
Bacillus	1314	1330	2816	2120	4276	8480	10120

The superiority of *Pseudomonas* sp. to degrade hydrocarbons over any other organism have been shown by numerous researchers [2,17]. The biodegradation potential of *Bacillus* sp. was compared with other species, and it as observed that it has a significant lower degradation potential while *Pseudomonas* sp. always shows a higher rate of degradation of hydrocarbons. The work of Sampaio *et al.*, 2022 further proved this where by 19 isolates were subjected to the degradation of 0.5% waste motor oil, and found *pseudomonas* sp. GD18 to be the ideal option due to its higher optical density (OD600) in M9 broth. However, *Bacillus* sp. has been employed with considerable achievement in the used engine oil degradation. The sea bacterial that produces biosurfactant, *Bacillus Licheniformis* LRK1 was found to be able to degrade about 24.23% of the oil in a minimal salt medium within the period of 21 days at 35 °C [19].

3.3 Detection of the *AlkB* gene (amplification of the gene)

Using the *AlkB* primer and the 1218bp band size for the *pseudomonas AlkB* gene was amplified. The genetic DNA fragment of *P. Aeruginosa* from the result of Agarose gel has two objectives. The first one was for the detection of the gene that was amplified while the second involved the insertion of the restriction enzymes at the restriction sites on the plasmid. It has become significant to determine the best primers to use in the amplification of *AlkB* gene due to the diversity of the enzyme in alkane biodegradation, therefore, the variation in sequence of the gene nucleotide in different bacteria was analyzed by various researchers [14]. Although, in this study, the primers that was adopted is from a single study of [15], the agarose gel result shown in figure 1 indicate that there was successful amplification of the gene 1218bp as seen in the bands.

Although, the used of combination primers are more successful than a single primer, for instance, the work of Jurelevicius, D. *et al.*, shows only 45% detection in the case of mono primer, while there was staggering 139% detection rate when combination primer was employed.

The 1218 bps of the *AlkB* gene amplified was introduces into the plasmid (pET-21a (+)) for this study, (figure 1). The most efficient plasmid vectors are the pET ones. They are competent in cloning and expression of recombinant proteins in *E. coli*.

3.4 Expression of the AlkB gene

The bacteriophage T7 regulate the expression of the target gene which are introduced into pET plasmid, the recombinant plasmid becomes pET-21a (+) *AlkB*, this was then inserted into competent cell of *E. coli* BL21 (DE3), A medium containing 10ug/ml of ampicillin was used to grow the *E. coli* containing the recombinant plasmid as it has an ampicillin resistance gene (amp.R) which allow them to be drt6xcf grow in the medium. The function of *AlkB* gene in some microorganism was studied by researchers, Hara A. *et al.*, analyses the function of the gene in *Rhodococcus* sp. strain CH91 that is able to survive on long-chain n-alkane as the soe carbon source, with the use of whole-genome sequencing, they found two AlkB gene AlkB1 and AlkB2, they determine the function of the gene by subjecting CH91 to degradation of n-alkane ranging from C16-C36, which induces the expression of gene, it was discovered that AlkB2 gene was significantly more up-regulated than AlkB1, and when the two genes were knockout, the growth of the organism and degradation of C16-C36 n-alkane significantly decrease.

Table 2: Present the Primers set for the amplification of AlkB Gene

AlkB gene Primers	Sequence	GC content (%)	PCR Product (bp)	Reference
Forward	5'cagGAATTCatgcttgagaaacacagagttc -3'	41	1218	[15]
Reverse	5'gacAAGCTTctacgatgctaccgcagagg -3'	60		[15]

Figure1: Demonstrate the left lane; DNA ladder 4500bp, Right lane; 1281bp of the amplified region of the DNA from *Pseudomonas*.

Figure. 2: indicated from the left lane; native plasmid, middle lane, the DNA ladder, and third lane; plasmid + AlkB gene; in general, indicated, this the successful cloning of the gene region

Figure 3: Showed the Gel Electrophoresis of the colony of the competent cells that contain recombinant plasmid (pET21a (+) *AlkB*); of *E. coli* BL21 (DE3). This is an indication that all the DE3 have transformed.

3.4 Comparison of biodegradation performance of the wild type and genetically optimized organism

Based on the residual oil obtained after the biodegradation, the gravimetric analysis result (figure 3.4) showed that there is variation in the biodegradation strength of the two bacteria. the best degradation percentage was found in the inocula that contained the GOO, where more than 90% of the UEO in all the 10 polluted soil was degraded, there was also a significant degradation in the pots inoculated with the wild type, of which more than 50% of the oil was found to be degraded. Concentration of hydrocarbons are among the factor affecting biodegradation rate [20], but his study uses same concentration of the

pollutant in all the inocula, but varies the concentration of the bacterial cells (CFU). From the result, it can be seen that there no significant deference within the groups, as both the wild type and the GOO group were able to degrade the UEO within the same rate. This shows that, the number of bacterial colony used in biodegradation of hydrocarbon pollutants, determine the success rate of the remediation process. Most of the bioremediation studies carried out placed more emphasis on the concentration of the contaminants, like the work of [21] that evaluated *Pseudomonas Putida*'s effectiveness at 1%, 2%, and 3% diesel. *P. putida* developed best at 1% diesel concentration, according to their findings; this may be due to its lower toxicity. In another investigation, *Rhodococcus* and *Pseudomonas* degrade about 80% of different concentration of UEO (0.5%, 1% and 1.5%) each [22]. This study further confirm that the catabolic ability of an organism is a very important factor in determining the success of complete mineralization of the pollutants in the environment, this is also seen in the work of [23] where they examined how four bacterial cultures degrade used engine oil in same concentration and under same condition, *Bacillus subtilis* PD6, *Bacillus sp.* PD9, *Enterobacter sp.* PD11 and *Bacillus sp.* PD14 were tested for their versatile catabolic capabilities, it was found the PD9 and PD 14 were the effective cultures out of the four by degrading 67.8% and 65.5% of the UEO respectively. The high degradation seen in the GOO group was due to the optimization of biosynthesis of enzyme alkane hydroxylase, although, microbes degrade pollutant better at lower concentration due to lower toxicity [24], a very active metabolic enzymes can enhance their ability to degrade pollutant at higher concentration successfully which was observed in this study.

Figure 4: Presented the % of oil degradation by different No. of CFU of wild type and GOO *pseudomonas Aeruginosa*. From our findings the GOO has the potential to degrade the used engine oil up to 90 %.

4.0 CONCLUSION

While a lot of used engine oil become catastrophic to the environment, searching for effectively used microbes that break down UEO has been on the increase. Consequently, of the two isolates examined in this study, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was found to be the most effective degrader, therefore, it was used for further investigation. The amplification of the gene was achieved before cloning into plasmid, and this provided the 1281bp of the amplified region of the *alkB* gene from *Pseudomonas*. There was also a successful transformation of the DE3. The outcome shows 90% of the oil was removed by the genetically

optimized organism. In addition, this study shows that, the number of viable cells in a medium is very significant in achieving complete mineralization of the pollutants irrespective of its toxicity.

REFERENCES

1. M. A. Ogunbisi^{1, 3} · O. O. Olujimi¹ · O. S. Sojini⁴ · Q. Xian² · T. A. Arowolo¹ *Occurrence, source and risk assessment of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in Ogun River and Lagos Lagoon, Southwest, Nigeria.* International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology 2022.
2. Muhammad, R., et al., *Stimulated bioremediation of soil contaminated with spent engine oil using organic wastes.* Science World Journal, 2022. **17**(2): p. 308-314.
3. Okpashi, V., et al., *Effect Of Agitated Chicken-Droppings for in Situ Bioremediation of Pahs in Spend Engine-Oil Contaminated Soil.* Journal of Bio-Science, 2021: p. 1-9.
4. Sales da Silva, I.G., et al., *Soil bioremediation: Overview of technologies and trends.* Energies, 2020. **13**(18): p. 4664.
5. Muhammad, A. and F.A. Adamu, *Biodegradation of Used Engine Oil by Pseudomonas sp. Isolated from an Automobile Workshop's Soil.* Journal of Environmental Microbiology and Toxicology, 2022. **10**(2): p. 59-62.
6. Adieze, I.E., *Effect of bioaugmentation on soil microbial populations and residual crude oil concentration of a polluted tropical soil.* Journal of Nigerian Environmental Society, 2012. **7**(3): p. 1-17.
7. Anyahara, J.N., *Effects of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) on the environment: A systematic review.* International Journal of Advanced Academic Research, 2021. **7**(3).
8. Patel, A.B., et al., *Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons: sources, toxicity, and remediation approaches.* Frontiers in Microbiology, 2020. **11**: p. 562813.
9. Benlaribi, R. and S. Djebbar, *Concentrations, distributions, sources, and risk assessment of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in topsoils around a petrochemical industrial area in Algiers (Algeria).* Environmental Science and Pollution Research, 2020. **27**(23): p. 29512-29529.
10. Yuan, T.-H., et al., *Relationship between renal function and metal exposure of residents living near the No. 6 Naphtha Cracking Complex: A cross-sectional study.* Journal of the Formosan Medical Association, 2021. **120**(10): p. 1845-1854.
11. Haq, I., A. Singh, and A. Kalamdhad, *Bioremediation for environmental sustainability toxicity, mechanisms of contaminants degradation, detoxification, and challenges.* Arsenic: environmental contamination, health hazards, and bioremediation approaches for detoxification. Elsevier, 2020: p. 121-142.
12. Balint, A. *Physical, chemical and toxicological properties of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in human exposure assessments to contaminated soil and groundwater.* in *MATEC Web of Conferences.* 2021. EDP Sciences.
13. García, M.M. and M.P.G. de Llasera, *A review on the enzymes and metabolites identified by mass spectrometry from bacteria and microalgae involved in the degradation of high molecular weight PAHs.* Science of the Total Environment, 2021. **797**: p. 149035.
14. Hara, A., et al., *Cloning and functional analysis of alkB genes in Alcanivorax borkumensis SK2.* Environmental microbiology, 2004. **6**(3): p. 191-197.
15. Al-Kanany, F.N. and R.M. Othman, *Cloning and Expression of Pseudomonas aeruginosa AlkB Gene in E. coli.* Journal of Pure & Applied Microbiology, 2020. **14**(1).
16. Jurelevicius, D., et al., *The use of a combination of alkB primers to better characterize the distribution of alkane-degrading bacteria.* PloS one, 2013. **8**(6): p. e66565.
17. Obi, C., et al., *Biodegradation of Spent Automobile Engine Oil in Soil Microcosms Amended with Cow Dung.* Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management, 2022. **26**(2): p. 255-263.

18. Sampaio, G.R.G., G.M.; da Silva, S.A.; de Almeida, A.P.; Pinaffi-Langley, A.C.C.; Rogero, M.M.; de Camargo, A.C.; Torres, E.A.F., *Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons in Foods: Biological Effects, Legislation, Occurrence, Analytical Methods, and Strategies to Reduce Their Formation*. . Int. J. Mol. Sci., 2021. **22**(6010).
19. Al-Hashimi, A.M.A., *Biodegradation Effect of some Bacterial Isolates on some Endocrine Disruptors (EDCS)* Al-Mustansiriyah Journal of Science 2018. **29**(2).
20. Lawal, A.T., *Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. A review*. Cogent Environmental Science, 2017.
21. Hussein I. Abdel-shafy, M.S.M.M., *A reiew on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons: source, eniromental impact, effect on human health and remediation*. egyptial journal of petroleum, 2016. **25**.
22. Olusola S. Amodu^{1, 3*}, Tunde V. Ojumu¹ and Seteno K. O. Ntwampe² *Bioremediating silty soil contaminated by phenanthrene, pyrene, benz(a)anthracene, benzo(a)pyrene using Bacillus sp. and Pseudomonas sp.: Biosurfactant/Beta vulgaris agrowaste effects* African Journal of Biotechnology 2016. **15**(22).
23. Jong-Su Seo¹, Young-Soo Keum^{1, 3} and Qing X. Li^{1,}, *Bacterial Degradation of Aromatic Compounds* International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health 2009. **6**.
24. Kalaivani, L.a., *Bacterial Degradation of Crude Oil by Gravimetric Analysis* Pelagia Research Library 2012. **3**(5).